

Enhancing Sustainable Competitive Advantage Through The Interaction of Innovative Behavior and Digital Technology

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ABSTRACT

The era of volatility characterized by rapid change, uncertainty, and global pressure requires organizations to adapt dynamically in order to survive and excel. This study aims to explore the role of innovative behavior and digital technology in creating sustainable competitive advantage in learning organizations in the midst of a constantly changing environment. The method used is the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) of 25 selected scientific articles from reputable international and national journals. The results of the study show that innovative behavior plays an important role in shaping organizational adaptability, while digital technology strengthens the efficiency, agility, and capacity of organizations to carry out sustainable innovation. The synergy between individual innovation and the application of digital technology can improve organizational capabilities in creating value and maintaining competitive advantage in the long term. This study also emphasizes the importance of digital capability, adaptive organizational culture, and leadership that supports digital transformation as the main supporting factors.

Keywords: Innovative Behavior, Digital Technology, Sustainable Competitive Advantage, Era of Volatility.

Introduction

The era of volatility characterized by rapid change, high uncertainty, and increasing complexity (VUCA: Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, Ambiguity) requires organizations to have strong adaptive capabilities (Bennett & Lemoine, 2014). One important strategy to survive and excel in this condition is through synergy between innovative behavior and the use of digital technology. Digital transformation has created structural changes in the way organizations operate, interact with customers, and compete in the market. This phenomenon is known as digital disruption, which is defined as the impact of digital technology that

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radically changes traditional business models and industry dynamics (Skog et al., 2018). Kraus et al., (2021) emphasize that digital transformation continues to change and develop rapidly, providing opportunities as well as challenges for all parties involved, so organizations must be ready to face change. In this context, organizations are required to be adaptive and innovative in seeking opportunities behind existing challenges to build competitive advantage strategies.

Employee innovative behavior and the use of digital technology are two important factors in responding to digital disruption. Both do not stand alone, but interact and strengthen each other in creating sustainable competitive advantage. This paper aims to reveal the synergy between innovative behavior and digital technology can be an effective strategy in facing the era of disruption and volatility. Innovative behavior refers to the tendency of individuals to generate, promote, and realize new ideas that are beneficial to the organization (Janssen, 2000; Alharthi, 2012; Susanto et al., 2023). On the other hand, digital technology provides the infrastructure and tools to realize this innovation in the form of new products, services, and processes. The interaction of the two forms an important foundation in developing sustainable competitive advantage. However, although both factors have proven important, the literature examining the synergistic relationship between innovative behavior and digital technology in the context of creating sustainable competitive advantage in the era of volatility is still fragmented. Therefore, this study aims to conduct a Systematic Literature Review (LSR) of 25 scientific articles to explore: (1) how innovative behavior contributes to organizational adaptability and agility, (2) how digital technology strengthens organizational innovation capacity and sustainability, (3) and how these two factors interact in forming a resilient and sustainable competitive advantage.

Digital disruption refers to fundamental changes caused by the adoption of digital technologies in various aspects of business and social life. The theory of “disruptive innovation” was first popularized by Christensen, (1997). (Laursen & Salter, 2006) explains how new technologies can displace dominant players by creating new markets or radically changing customer expectations. In the context of digitalization, disruption occurs when traditional companies face pressure to change due to the emergence of digital platforms, artificial intelligence (AI), and automation that accelerate innovation and efficiency (Skog et al., 2018). Digital disruption not only concerns the technological aspect, but also changes in business models, organizational structures, and patterns of interaction with customers.

According to Bughin et al. (2019), companies that do not respond quickly to digital disruption risk losing market relevance because they lose in the speed of adaptation and value creation. Digital transformation also requires organizations to not only adopt technology, but also change their mindset (digital mindset), work process structure, and strengthen organizational capabilities in dealing with rapid change. This is where the role of innovative behavior becomes important as

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the foundation of an organization's ability to deal with disruption. Meanwhile (Valero-Pastor et al., 2024) states that digital disruption is not only about technology, but about strategy, leadership and culture.

Innovative behavior refers to an individual's tendency to generate, promote, and implement new ideas in the work environment (Janssen, 2000; van Beusekom - Thoolen et al., 2024). According to (Khodakarami & Zakaria, 2015); Amabile (1988) that individual creativity influenced by intrinsic motivation, expertise, and organizational leadership style is the main foundation of innovative behavior. In a digitalized ecosystem, an individual's ability to innovate is one of the important assets in driving competitive advantage. Janssen (2004) divides innovative behavior into three stages: (1) ideation (generating new ideas), (2) idea promotion (convincing others about the value of ideas), and (3) idea implementation (realizing ideas in real form). In organizations facing digital disruption, individuals and teams that demonstrate innovative behavior are able to detect new opportunities, respond quickly to technological changes, and produce adaptive solutions.

Chaubey and Sahoo (2022) emphasize that innovative behavior does not occur spontaneously, but is influenced by organizational culture, transformational leadership, and reward systems that support experimentation and risk-taking. Innovation is rarely produced by genius individuals alone; innovation arises from culture and valuable experiences, collaboration, and responsiveness (Perry-Smith & Mannucci, 2017). Thus, innovative behavior is a vital element in building a resilient and responsive organization in the digital era.

Digital technology is not only an operational tool, but is now a strategic enabler that determines the direction and competitiveness of an organization. According to (Bouwman et al., 2019), digital capability that includes technology and information infrastructure, digital platforms, and data architecture enables companies to build agile and customer-oriented business processes. Various technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), big data analytics, and cloud computing have changed the way companies design products, manage internal processes, and reach markets. Proksch et al. (2021) show that adopting a targeted digital strategy can improve a company's digital capabilities, which in turn strengthens digital culture and readiness for innovation. In this context, digital technology does not stand alone, but is closely integrated with organizational processes and human capabilities. Successful digital transformation occurs when technology is combined with changes in mindset and innovative behavior. Therefore, a holistic approach that includes technology, people, and culture is essential. Digital technology refers to the use of advanced information and communication technologies such as artificial intelligence, cloud computing, big data, and the Internet of Things (IoT) in supporting an organization's business processes (Gao & Han, 2022; Khodakarami & Zakaria, 2015). Digital

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technologies enable automation, operational efficiency, and the creation of new, more flexible and adaptive business models. Organizational digitalization also drives the transformation of work culture, changes internal communication patterns, and increases cross-functional collaboration (Lo Presti et al., 2022; Liwafa et al., 2023). Research shows that high digital maturity is correlated with continuous innovation and superior organizational performance (Saleh & Brem, 2023; Bouwman et al., 2019).

Competitive advantage is the position of an organization's leadership in creating value compared to its competitors (Hellemans et al., 2022). However, in an era of volatility characterized by uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (VUCA), competitive advantage is no longer static. Organizations are required to build dynamic capabilities in order to adapt, innovate, and respond to change quickly. Teece, (2016) emphasized that dynamic capabilities include the organization's ability to (1) sense opportunities (sensing), (2) seize opportunities (seizing), and (3) transform internal resources (transforming). In the digital context, this means that organizations must be able to identify new technology trends, develop innovative digital-based solutions, and restructure business processes sustainably. Sustainable competitive advantage is an organization's superior position that is difficult for competitors to imitate and can be maintained in the long term (Ma, 2000; Alharthi, 2012). The Resource-Based View (RBV) theory states that valuable, rare, difficult to imitate, and irreplaceable (VRIN) resources are key to forming competitive advantage. In the digital and innovative context, competitive advantage is built through synergies between digital capabilities, organizational learning, and the ability to adapt to market and technological changes (Baquero, 2024; Erena et al., 2023).

Organizations that want to survive and excel in a rapidly changing environment must not only have cost advantages or product differentiation, but also the ability to learn, innovate, and transform quickly (Barney, 1991). The synergy between innovative behavior and the use of digital technology is the key to creating sustainable competitive advantage in the era of disruption. Competitive advantage is the ability of an organization to offer unique value that is not easily imitated by competitors. In an era of volatility, this advantage is not achieved through static resources, but through dynamic capabilities, continuous innovation, and digital transformation (Teece, 2016).

This article is prepared using a systematic literature review. To identify, select, and synthesize previous research findings. in a structured and transparent manner. This approach allows a comprehensive analysis of the contribution of innovation behavior and digital technology in creating sustainable competitive advantage, especially in the context of business environment volatility. Journal searches were conducted through reputable academic databases such as Scopus, ScienceDirect, Emerald Insight, Google Scholar, and ProQuest. There are 25 journals selected for

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further analysis and published between 2000 - 2025. The journals reviewed are in English and Indonesian. Focus on innovative behavior, digital technology, learning organizations and sustainable competitive advantage.

1.

From the literature analyzed, several additional key patterns emerge:

1. Synergy between digital transformation and innovative behavior: Digital transformation not only affects business processes but also drives innovative behavior at the individual and organizational levels (Gao & Han, 2022; Xiong et al., 2021).

2. The importance of organizational capabilities in supporting innovation: Capabilities such as digital readiness, change capability, and a clear digital strategy are key factors in driving sustainable innovation (Rizana et al., 2025; Supriharyanti & Sukoco, 2023).

3. The role of individuals in the innovation process: Individual creativity and digital readiness contribute significantly to organizational innovation, demonstrating the importance of human resource development in the digital era (Chaubey & Sahoo, 2022; Demerouti, 2025).

Table 1 Previous Studies on the Role of Innovation and Digital Transformation

No	Author	Article title	Findings	Findings related to Sustainable Competitive Advantage
1	Alharthi (2012)	<i>The role of innovation behavior in strategic development</i>	Innovative behavior drives adaptive strategies	Strategic adaptation supports long-term competitive advantage
2	Gao & Han (2022)	<i>Digital transformation and competitive advantage in volatile environments</i>	Digital transformation increases efficiency and flexibility	Fast market response creates dynamic advantages
3	Susanto et al. (2023)	<i>Innovative work behavior and firm agility</i>	Innovative behavior strengthens organizational	Organizational agility is essential for sustainable

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			agility	excellence
4	Namada & Mula (2018)	<i>Strategic capabilities for sustainability</i>	Strategic organizational capabilities are critical to sustainability	Strategic fit is the key to long-term excellence
5	Ma (2000)	<i>Competitive advantage: Sustained or temporary?</i>	Competitive advantage is dynamic	Unique resources strengthen long-term competitiveness
6	Asa et al. (2024)	<i>Leadership and innovation for sustainability</i>	Innovative leadership drives sustainable change	Innovation as the core of sustainable competitive advantage
7	Lo Presti et al. (2021)	<i>Digital maturity and innovation alignment</i>	Digital maturity strengthens organizational innovation	Digital integration increases competitive advantage
8	Farida & Setiawan (2022)	<i>Digital competencies and business sustainability</i>	Digital competencies support business resilience	Digital skills as a long-term competitive asset
9	Thi et al. (2023)	<i>Agile innovation in turbulent markets</i>	Agile innovation accelerates adaptation	Rapid adaptation as a key competitive advantage
10	Fatoki (2021)	<i>Entrepreneurial orientation and innovation performance</i>	Entrepreneurial orientation increases innovation	Product innovation creates sustainable differentiation
11	Liwafa et al. (2023)	<i>Technological capability and firm performance</i>	Technological capabilities increase productivity	Capabilities as a builder of long-term advantages
12	Kamardi et al.	<i>Organizational</i>	Organizational	Learning

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	(2022)	<i>learning and digital transformation</i>	learning supports digital transformation	organizations are more competitive and crisis-resistant
13	Saleh & Brem (2023)	<i>Digital strategy for innovation ecosystems</i>	Digital strategy as an enabler of innovation ecosystem	Innovation ecosystem creates sustainable excellence
14	Bauwman et al. (2019)	<i>Business model innovation in the digital era</i>	Business model innovation accelerates differentiation	New business models support competitive advantage
15	Juniarti et al. (2024)	<i>Knowledge capabilities and innovation</i>	Knowledge capabilities strengthen innovation	Knowledge management improves long-term competitiveness
16	Khodakarami & Zakaria (2015)	<i>IT capabilities and competitive advantage</i>	IT capabilities become a source of excellence	Integration of IT and business strategy strengthens market position
17	Perry-Smith & Mannucci (2017)	<i>Social networks and creativity</i>	Social networks strengthen creativity	Creativity strengthens competitive differentiation
18	Chaubey & Sahoo (2022)	<i>Employee creativity and innovation output</i>	Employee creativity supports innovative output	Sustainable innovation through empowerment
19	Supriharyanti & Sukoco (2023)	<i>Organizational change capability</i>	Change capability supports flexibility	Flexibility as dynamic competitiveness
20	Palmie et al. (2023)	<i>Microfoundations of digital innovation</i>	Individual micro capabilities are important for digitalization	Micro-macro synergy strengthens excellence
21	Biggio & Cortese (2013)	<i>Well-being and innovation</i>	Well-being supports innovative behavior	A healthy environment produces sustainable

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				innovation.
22	Demerouti (2025)	<i>Job demands-resources and innovation</i>	Balance of workload and resources drives innovation.	Positive working conditions support excellence
23	Parasuraman (2022)	<i>Work-family conflict and innovation</i>	Role conflict affects creativity	Stress management supports HR sustainability
24	Alge (2001)	<i>Electronic monitoring and trust</i>	Monitoring influences trust and innovation motivation	The right control system maintains competitive advantage
25	Kalischko & Riedl (2024)	<i>Digital control and performance</i>	Digital surveillance impacts innovation and performance	Ethical use of technology maintains competitiveness

Discussion

The results of the analysis of 25 journals show that innovative behavior and digital technology are not two independent variables, but rather mutually reinforce each other in creating sustainable competitive advantages, especially in the midst of a volatile business environment:

Innovative Behavior as a Driver of Adaptability

Individual and organizational innovative behavior plays an important role in increasing the capacity to adapt to external dynamics. Studies such as Alharthi (2012) and Susanto et al. (2023) indicate that employees who exhibit innovative behavior tend to be more proactive in seeking new solutions, driving efficiency, and responding quickly to environmental changes. Research by Fatoki (2021) and Kamardi et al. (2022) in the SME sector confirms that business sustainability is highly dependent on individual innovative capabilities, especially in the face of market uncertainty. Meanwhile, Namada & Mula (2018) and Liwafa et al. (2023) show that organizational learning and learning agility strengthen innovative behavior, making it an important capital in building organizational agility.

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Innovative behavior has also been shown to be influenced by organizational culture support, digital readiness, and leadership that supports creativity, as stated in the studies of Thi et al. (2023) and Chaubey & Sahoo (2022). This reinforces the importance of synergy between individual and structural factors in forming an innovative and adaptive work environment. In this case, if the organizational culture in question is a learning organization, which is open to change and adaptable to situations, it will be able to see opportunities and take advantage of technological advantages and encourage employees to innovate to create sustainable competitive advantages.

Digital Technology as a Determinant of Competitive Advantage

The second theme highlights how digital technology drives value creation and sustainable competitive advantage. Studies by (Gao & Han, 2022; Saleh & Brem, 2023) show that organizations that adopt digital strategies consistently experience acceleration in innovation, operational efficiency, and market response. Xiong et al., (2021) emphasize the role of digital capability as an important foundation that enables organizations to redesign business processes, create new business models, and explore and exploit digital knowledge simultaneously. Digital technology has also been shown to expand the space for employee collaboration and participation in the innovation process. The effective use of digital tools allows organizations to identify market needs faster, analyze data in real time, and personalize services, as found in studies (Bouwman et al., 2019; Lo Presti et al. 2021). This is in line with the dynamic capabilities theory which emphasizes the importance of sensing, seizing, and transforming in creating sustainable competitive advantage.

Synergy of Innovation and Technology in the Era of Volatility

This SLR also found that the synergy between innovative behavior and the use of digital technology is a key strategy to maintain competitiveness in a volatile business environment. Demerouti (2025) through the JD-R (Job Demands-Resources) approach stated that technological resources can mitigate high work demands and at the same time increase employee engagement and creativity. (Ma, 2000 & Saman et al., 2025) emphasized that competitive advantage no longer only comes from product uniqueness, but also from the organization's ability to innovate continuously by utilizing technology as a lever. Therefore, the success of future organizations is largely determined by the integration of innovative behavior, strengthening digital capabilities, and developing an adaptive learning organizational culture.

Digital Capability and Learning Organization

Digital capability encompasses an organization's ability to understand, adopt, and adapt new technologies quickly and effectively. (Cao et al., 2025) show that organizations with high digital capability are better able to recombine resources and knowledge to create innovations that are relevant to market needs. (Xiong et

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al., 2021) reinforce that digital tools encourage organizational learning and accelerate decision-making processes. In addition, digital technology also creates transparency, cross-functional collaboration, and encourages employee involvement in innovation.

Business Process Transformation and Digital Synergy with Human Factors in Organizational Culture

Digitalization is not only changing the way products or services are delivered, but also how internal processes are managed in real-time and adaptively. A study by Lo Presti et al. (2021) shows that the use of cloud-based technologies, AI, and automation provides advantages in terms of speed, accuracy, and flexibility. This allows companies to adapt to market pressures, reduce costs, and increase added value for customers. Digitalization also opens up opportunities for personalizing services based on customer data, improving user experience, and strengthening consumer loyalty which contributes to sustainable competitive advantage.

Although digital technology provides tremendous potential, literature such as (Khodakarami & Zakaria, 2015) and (Alharthi, 2012) emphasize that the success of technology adoption is highly dependent on the readiness of human resources and the support of organizational culture. Digital mindset, continuous training, and openness to change are the determinants of the success of digital transformation. Thus, digital technology is not a substitute for human resources, but rather an enabler that strengthens innovation and competitiveness. Organizations that are able to synergize technological capabilities and innovative behavior tend to be more resilient in facing external shocks.

Proposed Framework

This framework emphasizes that the success of organizations in facing the era of disruption depends not only on how quickly they adopt technology, but also on the extent to which they are able to shape innovative behavior and create a culture that supports transformation. Thus, an integrative approach between digital strategy, HR development, and strengthening organizational culture is the key to creating sustainable competitive advantage amidst the volatility of the business environment.

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Conclusions and Strategic Implications

This paper discusses how the interaction between innovative behavior and digital technology can be the key to creating sustainable competitive advantage in the era of digital disruption and business environment volatility. The results of the literature review and discussion show that:

1. Digital disruption is an external force that drives organizations to evolve strategically and operationally. Rapid technological change demands innovative and adaptive responses from all elements of the organization.
2. Innovative behavior acts as an internal driver that bridges technological potential with organizational value creation. Employees who are creative, proactive, and open to innovation are an important foundation in actualizing digital transformation.
3. Digital technology, although crucial, does not have a significant impact if it is not accompanied by the support of an innovative organizational culture, superior human capital, and adaptive strategies that are oriented towards learning.
4. Sustainable competitive advantage can only be achieved when the organization is able to synergize all components—technology, individual innovation, learning culture, and strategies that are responsive to market and technology dynamics.

Overall, this paper emphasizes that success in facing the era of disruption is not enough with technology investment alone, but requires a holistic approach that places people and a culture of innovation at the core of digital transformation.

Based on the conclusions above, there are a number of strategic implications that can be taken by organizations (both public and private sectors), especially in the context of a competitive market that is vulnerable to technological disruption:

- a. **Developing Innovative and Digital Leadership**
Organizations need to produce leaders who not only understand technology but are also able to create a work environment that encourages innovation. Transformational leadership and digital leadership are key in directing adaptation strategies amid rapid change.
- b. **Sustainable Investment in Human Capital**
Organizations must prioritize the development of digital and innovative competencies at every level of human resources. Continuous training, cross-functional learning, and digital mindset-based recruitment need to be the main strategies.
- c. **Building an Innovative Organizational Culture**
An organizational culture that supports learning, experimentation, collaboration, and tolerance for failure must be created and maintained. This kind of culture allows innovative behavior to emerge systematically, not sporadically.

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d. Designing Flexible and Responsive Business Models

Business models need to be redesigned to be adaptive to changes in technology and market behavior. Digital strategy should not be separate from the main business strategy, but should be an integral part of every strategic decision.

e. External Collaboration and Digital Ecosystem

Organizations need to expand their networks through collaboration with startups, universities, technology incubators, and research institutions to accelerate innovation.

In the digital age, excellence is often achieved through strategic collaboration, not competition alone.

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